

RELATIVE CLAUSE CONSTRUCTIONS IN ÒHÒRÍ YORÙBÁ

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Abstract

Ever since Bamgbose (1986) and Awobuluyi (1992, 1998) called for scholarly research attention on the study of Yorùbá dialects to increase the body of knowledge and understanding of the workings of the internal structures of Yorùbá language grammar, especially the standard form which has mounting unresolved issues, no serious work has been carried out on Òhòrí grammar, most especially on its relative clause constructions. The paper employed relevant data samples elicited from 12 adult native speakers of Òhòrí in Kétu, Ègùwá and Asá communities in Yewa North, Ogun State. It relies on Minimalist Program (Chomsky 1993, 1995, 1998, 2002) and Split-CP hypothesis (Rizzi 1997, 2003) as theoretical guides to analyse the data. The study discusses the structural derivations of relative clause constructions and shows that the four typology of relative clause constructions of Mark (2002) and Lehmann (1984) are employed in Òhòrí. It also demonstrates that a number of lexical items such as N, V, adverbs, etc. can be relativized in Òhòrí. Also, in contrast to what obtains in Standard Yorùbá where the relative clause introducer tí is optionally dropped in rare expressions (Awobuluyi, 1978:36), the introducer iyé is overtly obligatory in Òhòrí relative clauses. The study, therefore, proposes that the relative clause introducer iyé is the functional head that projects relative clause constructions in Òhòrí.

Keywords: *Relativization, Relative clause, Typology, Òhòrí, Yoruba*

INTRODUCTION

Relativization is a universal syntactic process cross-linguistically. As such, the syntactic construction is not unique to Òhòrí, not to talk of Yorùbá. However, different descriptions and definitions have been offered on relativization based on some parameters: syntactic and semantic parameters. For syntactic parameter, different scholars have proposed different definitions for relativization. Among them are Ilọri (2010:251) who sees relativization as;

a syntactic process of forming a relative clause construction. A relative clause is a subordinate clause in a complex IP projection that contains a constituent which has a kind of anaphoric link with another constituent serving as its antecedent in the main clause, such that the meaning of the complex clause involves two occurrences of a variable.

5. [matrix... [RC ... NP...]...]
6. Baba [tí [ó ra asọ dúdú]] nìyí
Father REL 1SG.HTS buy cloth black FOC-DEM
'This is the mother/woman who bought the black cloth.'

The structure in (5) indicates that the matrix contains a gap, which is filled by the whole relative construction, as shown in (6). While rounding off this section, we claim that all the definitions provided under each parameter employed above can be contextualized in Ọ̀họ̀rí.

1. Typology of Relative Clause in Ọ̀họ̀rí

This section discusses the typology of relative clause in Ọ̀họ̀rí. Syntactically, we assume following Lehmann (1984:149) and Mark (2002:30) that the typology of relative clause constructions are four: prenominal relatives, postnominal relatives, circumnominal relatives, and correlatives relatives.

1.1. Prenominal Relatives

This type of relative clause occurs in matrix and embedded clauses. The embedded clause is inserted inside the matrix clause, as evident in Ọ̀họ̀rí and Standard Yorùbá (SY) in (7) and (8).

Ọ̀họ̀rí

7. Obìì [ìyé [à tà]] wuyì
Kolanut REL 1PL.HTS sell fine
'The kolanut that we sold is fine.'

SY

8. Abà [tí [wón kọ]] dára.
Barn REL 3PL.HTS build good
'The barn that they built is good/beautiful.'

The structure of the prenominal relatives is given in (9).

9. [matrix... [RC ... N]...]

The examples provided in (7&8) match the structure of the relative clause type given in (9). The matrix clause subsumes the relative clause there.

1.2. Postnominal Relatives

This relative clause type occurs in matrix and embedded clauses. Unlike prenominal relatives that reside inside matrix clause, postnominal clause stands separately. The Ọ̀họ̀rí and Standard Yorùbá examples of this relative clause type are given in (10) and (11).

Ọ̀họ̀rí

10. Báyo rhí Sọlá [ìyé ó ñ kàwé.]
Bayo see Sọlá REL 3SG.HTS PROG read-book
'Bayo saw Sola who is /was reading.'

SY

11. Táyo na Olú [tí ó ñ pariwo.]
Tayo beat Olu REL 3SG.HTS PROG kill-noise

‘Tayo beats Olu who is making noise.’

The nominal word, which relative clause modifies in (10&11) resides outside the internal structure of the relative clause. The structure of the examples in (10 & 11) is configured in (12).

12. [s-matrix... [N RC]...]

The configurational structure in (12) equally aligns with the data provided in (10) & (11).

1.3. Circumnominal Relatives

This relative clause construction combines the head noun and the relative clause in a higher nominal expression. It is an internally headed relative clause. This is evident in (13) and (14) accompanied with the structure in (15).

Ọhọrí

13. Owó [iyé Ìyábò fí rha ata] kpò.
Money REL Iyabo use buy pepper much
‘The money that Iyabo used to buy pepper is much.’

SY

14. Àdá [tí Şolá fí pa eku] mú.
Cutlass REL Şolá use kill rat sharp
‘The cutlass that Sola used to kill the rat is sharp.’

15. [s-matrix ... [DP [CP-rel... DP]...]]

A close examination of the data in (13) and (14) shows that the examples are compatible with the structure in (15).

2.4. Correlatives

Correlative is a relative clause type that modifies the head noun. The relative clause contains a pronoun which is a referent to the modified relative head noun. It is an internally headed relative clause. Correlatives are bare clauses (Keenan, 1985:164), i.e., they are not full sentences. This is exemplified in (16) and (17).

Ọhọrí

16. Ọmọ ọlẹ [iyé ó fíjẹ lòní]
Child lazy REL 3SG.HTS do-work LOC-today
‘The lazy child who worked today’

SY

17. Ègbón Şolá [tí ó sọrò lánàá]
Elderly Şolá REL 3SG.HTS talk LOC-yesterday
‘Sola’s elderly brother who talked yesterday’

The structure of the correlative relative illustrated in (16) and (17) is schematized in (18) according to Mark (2002:30).

18. [N (...)] [RC ...] [s-matrix... (Dem)...]

However, in the spirit of information structure (Halliday 1967, Erteschik-Shir 2007), as will be contextualized in Ọ̀hòrí Yorùbá shortly, we modify the structure of (Mark, 2002:30) in (18) by removing the second part. Hence, what remains is the structure in (19).

19. [N (...)] [RC...]

Evidently, the description of correlative type of relative clause and the examples presented in both Ọ̀hòrí and Standard Yorùbá align with the structure provided. The phonetic representation of *ṣíjẹ* ‘to work’ in (16) is motivated by the pronunciation of the speakers of Ọ̀hòrí. Before the close of this section, we will like to mention some of the properties of relative clause according to (Mark 2002:30) and use the properties to draw the table of the relative clauses, described so far. Thus, the properties of relative clauses include: nominalization of relative clause (RC). RC is a satellite to noun relative (Nrel) or sentence matrix (Smatrix), Nrel is present in RC. RC is open or closed and gap/quasi-anaphor in RC represents Nrel, or anaphor in Smatrix represents Nrel + RC. The table of the four relative clause types explained so far is shown below according to (Mark, 2002:30).

Property	Correlative	CircumN	PostN	PreN
Nominalization of RC (yes/no)	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
RC is satellite to Nrel or Smatrix	N	-	N	N
Nrel is present in RC (yes/no)	Yes	Yes	No	No
RC is open or closed	Closed	Closed	Open	Open
Gap/quasi-anaphor in RC represents Nrel, or anaphor in Smatrix represents Nrel + RC	Anaphor	-	Gap	Gap

Table 1: The table of relative clauses in Ọ̀hòrí Yorùbá

2. Relativized Constituents in Ọ̀hòrí

A number of constituents can be relativized in Ọ̀hòrí. The relative marker in Ọ̀hòrí as mentioned above is *ìyẹ́*. The process of relativization in Ọ̀hòrí is via dislocation, i.e. raising of the targeted constituent to the specifier position of the relative clause. The relative clause marker immediately and directly follows the raised constituent in the dialect. Relativization can be expressed in small and complex clauses in Ọ̀hòrí. The constituents that can be relativized in the dialect are taken one after the other in the following sub-sections.

3.1. Relativized Constituents in Small Clauses

This section exclusively discusses the categorial items that could be relativized within the basic clauses in Ọ̀hòrí.

3.1.1. Subject Argument

One of the constituents that can be relativized is subject argument. The process of expressing it is achieved by raising the item to the leftward of the construction. There is overt relative operator (Ajiboye 2004, Adesola 2005, Ilọ̀rí 2017) that followed the raised NP immediately. There is presence of pro-form in the extraction site, which links the raised NP together, as expressed in (20) and (21).

20a. *Ìgè jẹ ẹ̀ba lí ìjẹkújẹ lí òdè.*
 Ige eat ẹ̀ba of badly LOC function
 ‘Ige ate ẹ̀ba badly at the function/event.’

- b. [Ìgè] [iyó jẹ ẹba lí ijekújẹ lí òdè]
 Ige REL-3SG.HTS eat ẹba of badly LOC function
 ‘Ige who ate ẹba badly at a/the function/event’

21a. Baba lu àhòn akékòó lí ìnàkunà.
 Father beat 3PL students of badly
 ‘The father beats the students badly/anyhow.’

- b. [Baba] [iyó lu àhòn akékòó lí ìnàkunà]
 Father REL-3SG.HTS beat 3PL students of badly
 ‘The father who beats the students badly/anyhow’

From the examples above, (20a) and (21a) are basic structures from which (20b) and (21b) are derived. We noticed that the pro-form which is a referent of the relativized item is *ó*. There are phonological constraints between the last vowel of the relative operator and the pro-form. The constraint is that for subject argument of relative clause construction to be well-formed in Ọ̀hòrí, the last vowel of the relative operator must get deleted, while contraction occurs immediately between the remnant of the relative operator and the pro-form. Invariably, there are two phonological processes occurring there: deletion and contraction, as shown below.

Base	Pro-form	Deletion	Contraction	Output
iyé	ó (HTS)	iyé	iy-ó	iyó

This is the case that happens between the relative morpheme and the pro-form in (20b) and (21b) which is glossed as ‘REL-3SG.HTS’. Subject-argument relative, as expressed in (20b) and (21b) reduces the strength of clause constructions in (20a) and (21a) to simple clause constructions. The data in (20b&21b) align with the *correlative relative* as a typology of relative clause construction explained above.

3.1.2. Object Argument

Object argument also passes the test of constituents that can be relativized in Ọ̀hòrí. When object (direct object) is relativized in Ọ̀hòrí, the object is displaced from the extraction site to the leftward. There is an overt relative operator that follows the displaced object immediately, as demonstrated below in (22) and (23).

22a. Àhòn ọ̀lopaa mu àhòn olè lí ònè-itura
 3PL police arrest 3PL thieves LOC hotel
 ‘The police arrested the thieves in an/the hotel.’

- b. [Àhòn olè] [iyé àhòn ọ̀lopaa mú <àhòn olè> lí ònè-itura]
 3PL thieves REL 3PL police arrest LOC hotel
 ‘The thieves whom the police arrested in an/the hotel’

23a. Àlání rhí Àyíndé lònòó lójáà
 Alani see Ayinde LOC-yesterday LOC-market
 ‘Alani saw Ayinde in the market yesterday.’

- b. [Àyíndé] [iyé Àlání rhí <Àyíndé> lònòó lójáà]

Ayinde REL Alani see LOC-yesterday LOC-market
'Ayinde whom Alani saw in the market yesterday'

The data presented in (22) and (23) indicate that (22a) and (23a) are basic structures, while (22b) and (23b) are derived structures [+REL CON]. The relative clause constructions in (22b) and (23b) equally weakens the potency of the full sentence structure in (22a) and (23a) to relative clause which is a modifier to the nominal head in (22b) and (23b). The examples in (22b&23b) match the *correlative relative* explained above.

3.1.3. Object of Preposition

The objective complement of a preposition (indirect object) can be relativized gallantly in Ọ̀hòrí. This follows the same process, i.e., dislocation of the objective item to the specifier position, which is followed by the overt relative operator, as exemplified in (24b) & (25b).

24a. Àmòkẹ̀ gbé ọ̀wọ̀ sí òkè.
Àmòkẹ̀ carry hand LOC mountain
'Àmòkẹ̀ lifted hands.'

b. [Òkè] [iyé Àmòkẹ̀ gbé ọ̀wọ̀ sí <òkè>]
Mountain REL Àmòkẹ̀ carry hand LOC
'The lifting that Àmòkẹ̀ lifts hands'

25a. Mò ó rha ilé sí Èkó.
1Sg HTS buy house LOC Lagos
'I bought a/the house in Lagos.'

b. [Èkó] [iyé mò ó rha ilé sí <Èkó>]
Lagos REL 1SG HTS buy house LOC
'The Lagos that I bought a/the house'

(24a&25a) are basic clauses, while (24b&25b) are relative clauses. The relativized items in (24b&25b) are displaced from the neutral domain to the discourse position for relativization. This is also a *correlative* type of relative clause.

3.1.4. Possessor's Relative

The next element can be relativized in Ọ̀hòrí is possessor of a head noun. When this is done, the possessor is raised to the SPEC domain of the relative clause and straightforwardly takes overt relative operator in the language. For the transformative construction [+REL] to be well converged, the displaced possessor replaces itself with a pro-form that functions syntactically as possessor in the higher construction, as exemplified in (26b&27b).

26a. Eijò kpa ajá ọ̀dè.
Snake kill dog hunter
'The snake killed the hunter's dog.'

b. [Ọ̀dè:] [iyé eijò kpa ajá ẹ̀]
Hunter REL snake kill dog POSS
'The hunter whom the snake killed his dog'

- 27a. Tádé jẹ ẹ̀bà Sọlá
Tádé eat ẹ̀bà Sọlá
'Tádé ate Sọlá's ẹ̀bà.'
- b. [Sọlá_i] [iyé Tádé jẹ ẹ̀bà ẹ̀_i]
Sọlá REL Tádé eat ẹ̀bà POSS
'Sọlá whom Tádé ate his ẹ̀bà'

The transformative constructions in (26b&27b) appear that the raised possessors leave a resumptive pronoun in the neutral position. This is another *correlative relative*.

3.1.5. Adverbial Relative

When adverbs are relativized in Ọ̀hòrí, it is also displaced to the extraposition and immediately takes overt relative operator in the proposition. This is illustrated in (28b&29b).

- 28a. Àjírún n sòrhò díèdíè.
Àjírún PROG say-word small-small
'Àjírún is talking slowly.'
- b. [Díèdíè] [iyé Àjírún n sòrhò <díèdíè>]
Small-small REL Àjírún PROG say-word
'Slowly that Àjírún is talking'
- 29a. Àmòkẹ̀ lọ kíákíá.
Àmòkẹ̀ go quickly
'Àmòkẹ̀ went quickly.'
- b. [Kíákíá] [iyé Àmòkẹ̀ lọ <kíákíá>]
Quickly REL Àmòkẹ̀ go
'Quickly that Àmòkẹ̀ went'

3.1.6. Verb Relative

The next constituent that fails not to pass the test of relativization in Ọ̀hòrí is verb (V). The approach is done via morphological process called gerund [+NOM], after which the nominalized verb is dislocated to the discourse position, depositing a copy of the verb in-situ. This is exemplified in (30) and (31).

- 30a. Ọ̀mọ ọ̀lẹ̀ kọ̀ jẹ itfɛ lóníí
Child lazy NEG do work LOC-today
'The lazy child did not work today.'
- b. [[ífɛ] [iyé ọ̀mọ ọ̀lẹ̀ kọ̀ jẹ itfɛ lóníí]
NOM-work REL child lazy NEG do work LOC-today
'The act of working that the lazy child did not work today'
- 31a. Sọlá jẹ ẹ̀bà lí ijẹkújẹ lóde
Sọlá eat ẹ̀ba of badly LOC-function/event
'Sọlá ate ẹ̀ba badly/anyhow at the function/event.'

- b. [Jíjẹ] [iyé Ṣọlá jẹ ẹ̀bà lí ijẹ́kújẹ lóde]
Nom-eat REL Ṣọlá eat ẹ̀bà of badly LOC-function/event
'The act of eating that Ṣọlá ate ẹ̀bà badly/anyhow at the function/event'

The data above show that (30a) and (31a) are basic clauses, from which (30b) and (31b) are derived. The verbs in (30a) and (31a) are nominalized via gerund and a copy of them remains in canonical position. This idea is common in most of Yorùbá dialects.

3.1.7. Verb Phrase Relative

Apart from the relativization of V, the data collected equally show that verb phrase (VP) can also be relativized in Ọ̀hòrí. The relativization of VP here is V plus its object. Just as explained in the V relative, the V in VP also goes through nominalization via gerund and dislocates the nominalized V with its object to the discourse position. Meanwhile, the full copy of the VP still remains in-situ, as demonstrated below.

- 32a. Ìjòbà yóó/á kpèsè ọ̀mí sẹ̀rìn ọ̀jáà
Government FUT provide water LOC-middle market
'The government will provide water in the market.'
- b. [Kpíkprésè ọ̀mí] [iyé ìjòbà yóó/á kpèsè ọ̀mí sẹ̀rìn ọ̀jáà]
Nom-provide water REL government FUT provide water LOC-middle market
'The act of providing water that government will provide water in the market'
- 33a. Ọ̀mọ ọ̀lẹ̀ kò jẹ itẹ̀ lónìí
Child lazy NEG do work LOC-today
'The lazy child did not work today.'
- b. [Íjẹ itẹ̀] [iyé ọ̀mọ ọ̀lẹ̀ kò jẹ itẹ̀ lónìí]
NOM-work REL child lazy NEG do work LOC-today
'The act of working that the lazy child did not work today'

The examples given in (32b) and (33b) appear similar with its counterparts in (30b) and (31b). The slight difference is the fact that the object of the V in (32b) & (33b) is successfully dislocated with the V to the extra-linguistic position, resulting to VP relative.

3.1.8. Adjunct Relative

From the data obtained, adjunct also passes the test of relativization in Ọ̀hòrí. Adjuncts are parts of a sentence which can be cut off without rendering the sentence meaningless. By adjunct, we mean prepositional phrase (PP), as shown in (34) and (35).

- 34a. Olùkó lu àhòn akékòó lí ìnákúná
Teacher beat 3PL student of severely
'The teacher beats the students severely.'
- b. [Lí ìnákúná] [iyé olùkó lu àhòn akékòó <lí ìnákúná>]
Of severely REL teacher beat 3PL student
'The manner that the teacher beats the students severely'

- 35a. Táyé kò mọ ọ́tí lí ìmọ́kímọ
 Taye NEG drink wine of anyhow
 ‘Taye did not drink the wine badly/anyhow.’
- b. [Lí ìmọ́kímọ] [iyé Táyé kò mọ ọ́tí <lí ìmọ́kímọ>]
 Of anyhow REL Taye NEG drink wine
 ‘The manner that Taye did not drink the wine badly’

The process of PP relative follows the pattern of object (direct object), object of preposition (indirect object) and adverbial relatives. Following the foregoing, we claim that Ọ̀họ̀rí operates correlative relative more than other typologies of relative clauses explained above.

3.2. Relativization in Complex Clauses in Ọ̀họ̀rí

However, relativization in Ọ̀họ̀rí is not restricted to categorial constituents within the basic structures. It is also possible to relativize complex structures in Ọ̀họ̀rí. Complex structures are structures that contain matrix and embedded clauses. We show the example in (36b).

- 36a. Olú fọ́ fú Ìdòwú fọ́lì kí ọ́ wá
 Olu say for Idowu COMP COMP 3SG come
 ‘Olu told Idowu that he should come.’
- b. [Fọ́lì kí ọ́ wá], Olú fọ́ fú Ìdòwú <Fọ́lì kí ọ́ wá> [Clausal Relativization]
 COMP COM 3SG come Olu say for Idowu
 ‘That he should come, Olu told Idowu.’

Evidently, the data in (36b) show that relativization is feasible in complex structures in Ọ̀họ̀rí. The embedded clause (36b) equally goes through relativization in Ọ̀họ̀rí with covert relative operator. Instead of overt relative marker following the relativized clause, there is presence of a comma which links the structures together as a single entity.

3. Dropping Introducer *tí*

Following Awobuluyi (1978:36), relative marker/introducer *tí* can optionally be dropped from relative clause qualifying *ẹ̀ni* (person), *ohun* (thing), *títí* (while, period) and several other nouns. Among the examples Awobuluyi cited are given in (37).

- 37a. Ẹ̀ni mo rí mo bá lọ
 Person 1SG see 1SG follow go
 ‘I went with the person I saw.’
- b. Ohun mo mú bọ́
 Thing 1SG take back
 ‘What I brought back’ (Awobuluyi, 1978:36)

The perception in (37a-b) is that the relative clause marker *tí* has been dropped immediately after *ẹ̀ni* ‘person’ (37a) and *ohun* ‘thing’ (37b). However, our observation is that there are instances, most especially in Ọ̀họ̀rí, where the relative clause marker cannot be dropped or muted. In such

event, the relative clause marker survives, but the qualifying nominal word is dropped. Examples of such events are given in SY and Ọhòrí in (38) and (39) respectively.

SY

38a. Èyí (tí) mo fẹ̀ nìyẹn
DEM 1SG want FOC-DEM
'That is the one I like/want.'

b. Ilé èyí (tí) mo kọ sí Èkó dára ju ilé èyí (tí) mo kọ sí
Ìbàdàn lọ
House DEM 1SG build LOC Lagos fine better house DEM 1SG build LOC
Ibadan go
'The house I built in Lagos is better than the house I built in Ibadan.'

Ọhòrí

39a. Ìyẹ̀ mò fẹ̀ liyẹ̀n/ìhùn
REL 1SG want FOC-DEM
'That is the one I like/want.'

b. Nné ìyẹ̀ mò kọ sí Èkó dára ju nné ìyẹ̀ mò kọ sí Ìbàdàn
lọ
House REL 1SG build LOC Lagos fine better house REL 1SG build LOC Ibadan
go
'The house that I built in Lagos is better than the house that I built in Ibadan.'

The parallel examples in (38) and (39) show that relative clause marker *tí* is optionally dropped in Standard Yorùbá examples in (38) by putting it in bracket but the relative clause marker *ìyẹ̀* survives in Ọhòrí examples in (39). We notice that a syntactic operation occurs in (39) which aids the survival of the relative clause marker in Ọhòrí. However, the first thing to be sorted out is that the relative clause marker *ìyẹ̀* in Ọhòrí should not be mistakenly taken for the demonstrative pronoun *èyí* 'this' in Standard Yorùbá. Ọhòrí has distinct item for *èyí* 'this' and that is *ìyẹ̀í* 'this', as exemplified in Standard Yorùbá and Ọhòrí in (40) and (41).

SY

40a. Mú èyí fún Ọláewé
Take DEM to Ọlaewe
'Give this to Ọlaewe.'

b. Táyọ̀ tí ra èyí
Tayọ̀ PERF buy DEM
'Tayọ̀ has bought this.'

Ọhòrí

41a. Mé ìyẹ̀í fỌláewé
Take DEM to-Ọlaewe
'Give this to Ọlaewe.'

- b. Táyò tin rha ìyèíí
Tayò PERF buy DEM
'Tayò has bought this.'

From the examples given in (40) and (41), it is clearly shown that Ọ̀hòrí has distinct equivalent item for the demonstrative pronoun èyí 'this'. Now, the question that may likely ring in one's mind is that, how come the relative clause marker survives and the qualifying demonstrative pronoun in Ọ̀hòrí examples (39) is dropped? The answer is not far fetch. The syntactic operation in (39) appears that if any relative clause construction where qualifying nominal item is èyí 'this' is to be rendered in Ọ̀hòrí, the demonstrative (qualifying) nominal word ìyèíí 'this' is dropped for the relative clause marker ìyé in Ọ̀hòrí. In such utterances, the relative clause marker ìyé in Ọ̀hòrí performs dual syntactic functions – as qualifying head noun of relative clause and as relative clause marker. This is unlike Standard Yorùbá examples in (38), where the relative clause marker is dropped and the qualifying head noun èyí 'this' survives. Another simple way presenting this syntactic manifestation in the two varieties is to claim that the demonstrative pronoun ìyèíí 'this' in Ọ̀hòrí cannot co-occur side-by-side with the Ọ̀hòrí relative clause marker ìyé. If in any occasion such utterances arise in Ọ̀hòrí, the demonstrative pronoun ìyèíí 'this' as a matter of fact bows or mutes for the relative clause marker ìyé to take charge. This syntactic abomination in Ọ̀hòrí is against what happens in Standard Yorùbá, where the relative clause marker tí can optionally be dropped for the qualifying demonstrative head noun èyí 'this' in relative clause construction and at the same time, the two items, i.e., èyí and tí, can co-exist together. We are not surprised with this revelation in Ọ̀hòrí because (Awobuluyi, 1978:36) equally submitted that dropping the introducer tí is actually rare in Standard Yorùbá, though not in some of its dialects. Thus, Ọ̀hòrí is one the Yorùbá dialects which its relative clause marker is rarely dropped. In other words, Ọ̀hòrí relative clause marker regularly and overtly presents.

Another interesting discovery is that, in conditional clauses where the relative clause marker tí (though it is a conditional marker there) shows up in Standard Yorùbá, Ọ̀hòrí has unique marker, which is equivalent to tí in this context and that is *njí*. The conditional clause marker *njí* is never dropped in Ọ̀hòrí conditional clauses but survived. Let us consider the Standard Yorùbá and Ọ̀hòrí examples in (42) and (43).

SY

42a. Tí mo bá lówó mà á kólé
COND 1SG if LOC-money 1SG FUT build-house
'If I have money, I will build a house.'

- b. Mà á kólé tí mo bá lówó
1SG FUT build-house COND 1SG if LOC-money
'I will build a house, if I have money.'

Ọ̀hòrí

43a. Njí ò bà nówó mà à kóné
COND 1SG if LOC-money 1SG FUT build-house
'If I have money, I will build a house.'

- b. Ma à kóné njí ò bà nówó
1SG FUT build-house COND 1SG if LOC-money

‘I will build a house, If I have money.’

The assumed Ọ̀hòrí relative clause marker in (43) overtly shows up. Even in Standard Yorùbá, the assumed relative marker in (42) is obligatorily present, otherwise, the expressions in (42) will result to ill-formed utterances. In a nutshell, while the relative clause marker is optionally dropped in rare utterances in Standard Yorùbá, Ọ̀hòrí relative clause marker overtly and regularly presents in its relative clause constructions. We navigate to the derivation of the relativized constituents discussed so far.

5. Derivation of the Relative Constructions in Ọ̀hòrí

The goal of this section is to discuss the projection process of relativization in Ọ̀hòrí. Based on the data obtained and the number of constituents that passed the test of relativization in Ọ̀hòrí, we are going to discuss four structural projection types of relative clause in Ọ̀hòrí. The first structure accounts for the constituents that leave a pro-form in the canonical position after dislocation to the discourse position for relativization, such as subject argument and N possessor. The second structure captures the constituents that leave no phonetic item in the extraction sites after dislocation to the leftward for relativization, such as object argument, object of preposition, adverb, and propositional phrase. The third structure accounts for the constituents that drop a copy of its property in-situ after raising to the specifier position for relativization, which include verb and verb phrase. The fourth structure caters for the complex structure (clausal projection), which is similar to the object argument projection and its counterparts but has zero nucleus in its projection. However, following Rizzi (1997, 2003) which states that complementizer phrase (CP) analysis should be split into different function projections that made it up, namely Force Phrase (ForceP), Focus Phrase (FocP), Interrogative Phrase (InterP), Topic Phrase (TopP), and Relative Phrase (RelP) simply because each of them is separable from one to the other in discourse. Thus, we adopt Relative Phrase (RelP) in our projection analysis. Consequently, we propose in this paper that relative clause construction in Ọ̀hòrí Yorùbá is headed by the Rel⁰ head which is morphologically realized as *iyé*, merges with IP/TP as complement to derive its syntactic projection. The projections fall under the sketch [RelP... [Rel... [IP/TP...]]].

5.1. Subject Argument and Possessor’s Projection

The structure here accounts for the subject argument and possessor’s projection. Before the start of projection, the relativized constituent *olùkó* scopes to the Spec-RelP. Thus, the projection process is that the head of RelP, Rel which is morphologically represented with *iyó* [+Rel-Pro-form] internally merges with the complement, IP/TP *lu àhòn akékọ̀ọ̀ lí ìnàkunà* to project Rel-bar and Rel-bar projects into RelP *iyó lu àhòn akékọ̀ọ̀ lí ìnàkunà*. There is extended projection principle (EPP) in the structure. Hence, the SPEC, *olùkó* attracts RelP to project maximally. This derivation equally accounts for the possessor’s projection, which leaves a pro-form in the canonical domain. The derivation is illustrated below in (44).

44.

5.2. Object Argument, Object of Preposition, Adverb and Prepositional Phrase Projection

The next structural projection caters for the object argument, object of preposition, adverb and prepositional phrase projection. As schemed out in (45) below, the relativized element, *Àyindé* is firstly dislocated to the Spec-RelP. Thus, the locus of the RelP, Rel⁰, morphologically represented as *iyé* internally merges with IP/TP as complement, *Àlání rhí lònòò lójáà* which projects Rel-bar and later projects into RelP, *iyé Àlání rhí lònòò lójáà*. To satisfy the EPP, the SPEC, *Àyindé* attracts the RelP, which now projects maximally. This derivation also captures object of preposition, adverb, and prepositional phrase. The structural representation is presented below in (45).

45.

5.3. Verb and Verb Phrase Projection

The third structure accounts for the projection of verb and verb phrase. The projection type indicates that the verb to be relativized, *fe* has been copied, nominalized and displaced to the specifier position before the projection kicks off. Therefore, the head of the RelP, Rel⁰ represented by *iyé* internally merges with the IP/TP, *omọ òlẹ̀ kọ fe itfe lóní*, which projects Rel-bar and the Rel-bar later projects RelP, *iyé omọ òlẹ̀ kọ fe itfe lóní*. The projection also has EPP. Thus, the SPEC, *fife* attracts the RelP for maximal convergence. The derivation (Chomsky, 1995) equally accounts for the verb phrase projection, where the verb is copied, nominalized and dislocated with its object to the specifier domain. The V and VP projection is a pre-syntactic derivation type because the nominalized V, though valued, it is copied and raised to the Spec-RelP outside the scope of the relative structure but not deleted. If the nominalized and valued V is deleted in the extraction site, the derivation will crash. The configurational derivation is illustrated below in (46).

46.

5.4. Clausal Projection

The last projection in this section is the derivation of the complex structure which is labelled as Clausal projection here. The relativized constituent in (47) below, *fòlì kí ó wá*, firstly pipe pied to the discourse position. The Rel⁰, which has zero representation internally merges with the IP/TP, *Olú fọ́ fú Ìdòwú* which projects Rel-bar and the Rel-bar projects into RelP. Thus, the SPEC, *fòlì kí ó wá* attracts the RelP for maximal derivation. The structural diagram is schematized beneath in (47).

6. Conclusion

This paper has critically examined relative clause constructions in Ọ̀hòrì Yorùbá. It discussed four relative clause types in Ọ̀hòrì Yorùbá, as contained in (Mark 2002) and Lehmann (1984). It emphasized that out of the four relative clause constructions, Ọ̀hòrì operates correlative relative above other types, as demonstrated in the data presented under relativized constituents. The article also contended that Ọ̀hòrì relative clause operator is rarely dropped across its relative clause constructions. Even, if the relative clause operator *iyé* features side by side with demonstrative pronoun *iyéìì* ‘this’ (*èyí* ‘this’ in Standard Yorùbá), the demonstrative item *iyéìì* ‘this’ is muted for the relative clause operator *iyé*. The article rounded off its discourse by showing and discussing the structural derivations of the constituents that passed relativization test in Ọ̀hòrì.

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End Notes

¹Just like when subject is focused in Standard Yorùbá, there is a pro-form *ó* showing up in the canonical position of the focused subject. This syntactic event equally occurs in subject relative in Òhòrí. Different submissions have been reported on the pro-form *ó* in the literature. Awobuluyi

(1988) sees the pro-form *ó* as preverbal modifier. Ajiboye (2005:104-105) analyzes the pro-form *ó* as inflectional element that instantiates Specifier-Head agreement in IP.